

WORKING WITH COMPUTER PROGRAMS IN MODERN CONSTRUCTION DESIGN

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Abstract: the article contains information about the design programs used in the construction industry in developed countries and in our country.

Key words: project, computer design, drawing, program

A local construction company may not need international attention, but online presence and search engine optimization are essential. After deciding to create a website, the user needs to choose a viable platform. WordPress has been a favorite of the internet community for years because it offers an affordable, one-stop service. Countless blogs and company web pages are built on WordPress, with new posts appearing on millions of sites every day. These large numbers are a plus, but there is also a downside: there is a risk of getting lost in the crowd. How can your construction company website be different from others? WordPress has a diverse and professional community of developers and designers. Their themes, whether they're premium versions or free, stripped-down alternatives, are capable of adding a whole new level of customization to your site. Such settings make your site unique and memorable for your users. Let's take a look at the best WordPress builder themes.

Javelin is a robust, professional multi-page WordPress website theme. The theme includes a collection of demo sites and page templates that you can deploy with just one click. They are polished for specific applications and cover a range of industries and interests. Javelin is the perfect theme for webmasters who want to

create an online marketplace for their projects. Construction company websites especially benefit from Javelin's wide range of features and layouts: custom demos, handy shortcodes, service packages, and price lists. Javelin is packed with stunning layouts, portfolios and data layouts to showcase the best work done and services provided.

TheGem is a robust, tech-savvy, fast-loading, multi-user theme for WordPress. The theme is packed with over 40 conceptually unique demo site templates that cover a range of industries and businesses across all sectors. Although it especially shines when it comes to the construction industry. The theme has many options for single web page and multi-page sites. Features: customizable gallery options and layouts, widgetized headers, footers and sidebars with a rich collection of useful widgets, handy shortcodes to make it easier to work with your price lists, service packages, and presenting all information in an attractive presentation. With TheGem, you get a fully functional online store page where you can sell your services directly to your visitors.

Industrial is a manufacturing business WordPress theme that uses the amazing Visualizer page builder. With the theme, you get many custom features for the business models of your chosen industry. The industry uses one-click demo import. The template includes many icons (Awesome font and 7 strokes) related to the themes. Fixed page width and full screen version available. The theme is suitable for both large companies and small businesses. Industrial has many shortcodes to help you avoid coding for the construction site. It also uses WooCommerce to customize any storefront. Industrial has a special cost calculator to accurately calculate customer budgets. Finally, it uses the Native WordPress Customizer and is WPML compatible.

Neer is a modern WordPress theme suitable for many business sectors. It covers machinery, petroleum and architecture, construction and many more. Design your site the way you want it. Neer provides the necessary tools to achieve this goal.

Thanks to the WPBakery page builder, you don't need any special design skills, everything is intuitive. MegaMenu, Fonts Awesome, and Redux give your site minimal design options. ContactForm 7 can be used to communicate with potential customers. Your site will impress users on both desktop and mobile devices thanks to its flexibility. WooCommerce together with WPML ensures that you can do business all over the world. One-click demo installation, detailed documentation, and support make Neer a perfect choice.

This responsive WordPress theme is suitable for websites of architecture firms, construction companies and freelance architects. There are many features and customization options. With the Builder Page Editor, you can create stunning web pages. Download speeds are excellent, resulting in excellent customer service. If you want to commercialize your products or services, you can create your own online store with WooCommerce. The build theme provides affordable translation and multilingualism with built-in WPML plugin support. Considering that multilingual pages attract more views, it contributes to the growth of your site. The theme is integrated with Revolution Slider and includes 15 HTML files. Also included are 11 PSD files. There are 6 different post types: Services, Clients, Projects, Employees, Slider and Testimonials. This makes it easy to categorize your content. The build includes 9 widgets with multiple fields and a practical dropdown menu.

Massive Dynamic is a clean and clear, responsive, multi-user WordPress website. It is a set of tools for creating professional-quality websites: a large set of development tools, predefined templates and layouts, customizable shortcodes and additional capabilities available in real time thanks to the Live Website Builder feature. Massive Dynamic combines page builder capabilities with unique designs, beautiful and stylish website demos and template pages for maximum flexibility. They are highly customizable for different markets and applications. Many of these templates are designed specifically for building site development. Massive Dynamic includes the Go Pricing plugin, which allows you to quickly create creative,

attractive and dynamic pricing plans and pricing for your services. The template includes various portfolio options and layouts, so you can showcase your work in the best possible way. With Portfolio Live Redrange, you can resize and resize your photos in real time.

KALLYAS is an easy-to-use, multi-functional, responsive multipurpose WordPress theme. This theme has all the tools you need to effectively design and build modern websites in minutes. You don't have to write the code yourself. With KALLYAS, you get access to a large collection of sophisticated, professionally designed, ready-made demo websites and template pages. Customizing your layouts is easier than ever with the built-in, plugin-free page editor. The included Slider Revolution theme offers a variety of custom slider styles. KALLYAS is ideal for hosting websites of construction firms, contractors, landscapers and design studios. The theme includes a live portfolio, attractive and stylish galleries, user-friendly business features such as Pricing Tables and MailChimp, newsletter subscription and the beautiful visual style of Parallax.

Handel is a multi-user WordPress theme. The template offers great demos for specific niches. Adaptability and versatility are its main advantages. Handel offers demonstrations for all business sectors, including construction, engineering and architecture. In this demo you will find many gallery and portfolio sections and you will understand how beautifully you can organize your work. The theme offers a modern concept suitable for both beginners and professionals. The template is fully SEO optimized and clean code based. Access to social networks is opened using share buttons. Handel is about creating charts, personal pages and contact forms. The template includes a Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) block, recent posts, and comments sections. Handel Revolution supports slider and MailChimp integration.

Pithree is a custom WordPress theme. It is a great option for architectural agencies, construction companies and equipment suppliers. The template has four main page options and a child theme. Pithee focuses on configurability by combining

several cool features. It offers integration with Visual Composer, Slider Revolution and Redux. WooCommerce and WPML plugins are available for e-commerce and translations. Pithree provides great visual appeal for layout elements. You'll get great typography as well as icons from Font Awesome and Google font collections. Custom backgrounds are available, including Parallax and wide formats. Get the theme now with upcoming updates and 6 months of support from G5Theme!

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